

ЛЕЧЕНИЕ ДЕТЕЙ НА СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКОМ ПРИЕМЕ ПРИ ПРИМЕНЕНИИ СЕДАЦИИ

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DENTAL TREATMENT OF CHILDREN WITH SEDATION

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Аннотация

Закись азота – это фармакологический препарат, используемый в медицине для снятия психоэмоционального напряжения, т. е. для того, чтобы пациент перестал испытывать страх и другие негативные эмоции. Закись азота (ЗАКС) входит в список основных лекарств ВОЗ (Всемирной организации здравоохранения), разрешена к применению в РФ. Применение закиси азота в детской стоматологии позволяет добиться высоких результатов, так как облегчает работу врача и вызывает у ребёнка положительное впечатление от посещения стоматолога.

Abstract

Nitrous oxide is a pharmacological drug used in medicine to relieve psycho-emotional tension, and to eliminate the patient's fear and other negative emotions. Nitrous oxide (NOS) is included in the list of main drugs of the WHO (World Health Organization), approved for use in the Russian Federation. The use of nitrous oxide in pediatric dentistry makes it possible to achieve high results, as it facilitates the work of a doctor and gives the child a positive impression from visiting a dentist.

Ключевые слова: стоматология, седация, закись азота.

Keywords: dentistry, sedation, nitrous oxide.

Introduction.

One of the most challenging current health issues proves to be the high dental morbidity of children and adolescents. The specifics of the physiological and psychological development of a child, the labor intensity and duration of treatment procedures, as well as the emotional unprepared parents explain the fact that for many children, dental treatment is a real stress factor.

The child's behavior is guided by emotions that can impede the work of the dentist and affect the quality and prognosis of treatment. Visiting a dentist for a child is associated with a forced position in a chair with an open mouth, specific sounds, bright light, unknown smells, as well as communication with strangers. All these factors give rise to tension and fear. Memory for negative

effects can arise and become fixed in the child's mind for all his life.

To provide high-quality dental care, a child needs to create special conditions in which he will feel calm and comfortable. The solution of the problem of such treatment is possible with the use of nitrous oxide sedation [2, p.7].

Background.

The prevalence and intensity of tooth caries has increased among the child population in recent decades in Russia largely, due to the unsatisfactory hygienic state of the oral cavity in children of early and pre-school age. The increase of the carious process in temporary teeth leads quickly to complications of caries, and premature loss of teeth. From an early age, children already need different types of dental care, which is a great clinical and organizational problem for children's dentists.

The vast majority of young patients are afraid of dental treatment, especially those who have already had negative experience with the dentist. Children often refuse from treatment or, unfortunately, sometimes doctors are forced to treat young patients against their will.

Children are often afraid of the specific situation of the dental clinic, and physiologically cannot safely endure long-term procedures, while the treatment of the oral cavity in normal conditions requires an average of 3-4 or even more visits, and as a result, it turns into chronic stress for them, provoking dentistry phobia.

Faulty communication between doctor and young patient makes the qualified dental care unrealistic or even impossible, so children are more widely used than adults in general pain relief or treatment in sedation conditions.

However, the method of general pain relief for the rehabilitation of children with a negative attitude towards dental treatment is used in a limited number of medical institutions.

Moreover, the method of sedation with preserved consciousness also deserves attention. It should be noted that this type of anesthesia aid is of a great concern and constantly growing. In our country, for many reasons, including organizational ones, this type of anesthesiological allowance in dental treatment is used on rare occasions in adult patients, and only in single clinics in children.

Sedation (from Latin *sedatio*) means an artificially caused reversible state of the body, which results in minimal depression of consciousness; protective reflexes, the ability to breathe independently and verbal contact are preserved. Consequences of sedation are reduced psychomotor excitation and affective tension, weakened responses to external stimuli, depressed aggression.

Nitrous oxide (oxygen sedation) is most often used in pediatric dentistry. Nitrous oxide is a chemically stable compound that is an odorless and colorless gas at room temperature. N_2O has high diffusion capacity, which is 30 times higher compared to nitrogen, which is the main component of atmospheric air. As a result of this phenomenon, nitrous oxide has a pharmacological property beneficial from the standpoint of anesthesiology rapid achievement of saturation in blood and

tissues, and the same rapid elimination from the body [3, p. 37].

This chemical compound was discovered by the English chemist Joseph Priestley in 1772, the properties of this gas being thoroughly studied later in 1796 by his compatriot Humphrey Davy. After auto experiments he was the first to express the idea of the possibility of its use for anesthesia. For this, in 1799, H. Davy called nitrous oxide "laughing gas" ("Lach-gas" in German, a term is still being used today). Nitrous oxide was first used for anesthesia in 1844 by the American dentist Horace Wells on his own, while his colleague John Riggs removed a healthy molar from the subject. Then in 1868 it was established that the N_2O only physically dissolves in the blood, without changing the chemical composition of the latter, that is, it is present in plasma in a free state. In the same year, Professor of Surgery from Chicago Edmund Andrews began to combine inhalation of nitrous oxide with the addition of oxygen, which made it possible to use anesthesia for a longer time.

Nitrous oxide anesthesia was successfully applied in Russia in 1869 for the first time by L. Bernardo-Berkmeer, who proposed painless tooth removal, as well as surgeons S.P. Botkin and S. Klikovich used it during childbirth. In 1888, this gas was used by St. Petersburg's dentists for anesthesia. Since 1948 nitrous oxide - oxygen sedation is used in countries with progressive dentistry [1, P. 68-69].

The pharmacological effect of the N_2O is manifested in the fact that it inhibits the transmission of nerve impulses to the CNS, changes the cortical-subcortical relationships, non-specifically interacting with the membranes of neurons.

Nitrous oxide causes a certain analgesic result associated with its antinociceptive effect, which develops due to the release of opioid peptides in the brain stem, activation of the descending inhibitory pathways and the sympathetic α_1 -adrenergic system, the release of norepinephrine in the neurons of the posterior horns of the spinal cord. The upstream path of transmission of pain impulses from the periphery to the center at the segmental level is modulated. The analgesic effect of the N_2O is not enough for dental manipulation, therefore, local anesthesia should be additionally performed [5, p. 16].

According to the "American Society of Anesthesiologists" (ASA) classification m sedation is divided into the following levels:

1) Mild sedation – the patient is awake, is in contact with the doctor, but his informative function and coordination can be reduced. This level corresponds to from 0 to 2 points on the Richmond scale of agitation-sedation.

2) Mean sedation – depression of consciousness, patients respond to a slight tactile stimulus, and are able to interact with a doctor, there is no need to support airway patency, adequate spontaneous breathing and cardiovascular function are preserved. This level corresponds to 3 points on the Richmond scale of agitation-sedation.

3) Deep sedation – patients cannot be easily awakened but respond to repeated or painful stimulus, airway patency support may be required, spontaneous breathing may be impaired, cardiovascular function preserved. This level corresponds to 4 points on the Richmond scale of agitation-sedation [4, P. 115-116].

Indications for the use of NOS in pediatric dentistry are:

1. the need to relieve moderate fear of dental intervention in a child capable for treatment;
2. increased emetic reflex;
3. traumatic interventions (local anesthesia, removal, preparation of the carious cavity);
4. long-term treatment.

Contraindications to NOS are:

1. irresistible fear in a child after receiving negative treatment experience from a dentist and unwillingness to make contact with a doctor;
2. mental illness and intellectual disabilities that impede the possibility of bilateral contact;
3. impaired nasal respiration (adenoids, ARVI), when the child will breathe with his mouth and will not be able to use the nasal mask;
4. overcrowded stomach, and nausea and vomiting may occur (the last meal should be carried out 2 hours before the start of sedation);
5. hyper excitability, since there is a possibility of a paradoxical response to sedation.

The doctor, analyzing the behavior of the child at the consultation, can predict the effect of NOS on the patient.

Aim of the work. To carry out the comparative analysis of clinical records of the children being treated in children's clinics of LLC "Childhood" of Chita under a sedation and to study activity of doctors during implementation of the protocol of a sedation.

Materials and methods. The research was carried out on the basis of children's clinics LLC "Childhood" in the city of Chita. One hundred and fifty case histories of patients aged 2 to 15 years were analyzed. Observation and study of doctors' activities during the implementation of the sedation protocol in the treatment of 15 children was studied.

Results. Analysis of case histories of patients treated at LLO "Childhood" indicates that most often sedation was used in children aged 3 to 8 years and lasted about an hour. The difference in the use of NOS in boys and girls was not statistically found, since psycho-emotional differences in children have not yet been formed at this age [2].

The staff of LLO "Childhood" worked according to the protocol for the use of nitrous oxide in working with children. The N₂O was supplied using special equipment. The Matrix apparatus is a rotameter (mixer) that allows to adjust the ratio of gases in the mixture, a reserve bag, a breathing circuit with a nose mask and a source of gases (cylinders). In a playful form, a mask was tried on and the doctor explained to the child what would happen to him. It is important to obtain the voluntary consent of the patient to put on a mask – this is the first component of success.

The introduction into the sedation state began with the supply of 100% oxygen at a rate of 4-6 l/min and

the gradual addition of nitrous oxide, the permissible N₂O concentration being 70%. The most optimal ratio at which the planned treatment can be carried out is 30% nitrous oxide and 70% oxygen.

However, the control of nitric oxide concentration depends on its effect, and in each case it is an individual indicator that was recorded in the map.

After the start of inhalation, the blood is saturated with gas in 5-7 minutes. As soon as inhalation stops, the gas is completely removed by the lungs unchanged. A feature of NOS, unlike other sedative drugs, is the rapid onset of sedation and the absence of a trace effect: it is completely eliminated from the body within 5-10 minutes due to inhalation of 100% oxygen at the final stage [6].

The average sedation time was 7 minutes with an extreme oscillation limit of 5 minutes to 12 minutes. We did not find any relationship between the duration of the onset of the effect of N₂O administration with the age of the child and, accordingly, with his weight.

Symptoms of sedation were manifested in the form of a comfortable, relaxed state, satisfactory spirit, soft, inhibited body movements, lack of resistance, deep breathing, decreased movement of eyes, easily fixed gaze, reduced sound perception. Patients were disoriented and easily suggestive.

A pronounced effect was marked in 23% of children. The patients were in a semi-sedate calm state with isolated weak motor reactions. HR was reduced by an average of 10 bpm, RR - by 5, BP did not change.

Almost all children showed a good results (75%), which was manifested by calm behavior. The child did not sleep, but was clearly inhibited. Occasionally, crying and sluggish movements of the limbs were observed. The hands were dry, warm; HR was reduced by 8 bpm; RR - by 2, BP remained at baseline.

Only 2% of patients showed a weak effect. Their heart and respiratory rate remained almost at baseline, blood pressure increased in some children, but slightly (by 5-10 mm Hg). Moderate motor agitation, monotonous crying were noted. Completion was carried out under the residual influence of nitrous oxide. The recovery from sedation was smooth and ended with inhalation of 100% oxygen for 3-5 minutes.

Conclusion.

Thus, the method of sedation with preserved consciousness does not negatively affect the general condition and behavior of children and provides the possibility of oral sanitation with significantly calmer behavior of children.

The assessment of nitrous oxide agents' sedation scale in pediatric dentistry allows to make the following conclusions:

1. The NOS method creates comfortable conditions for both the patient and the dentist, while improving the quality and volume of the dental intervention performed, which makes it possible to fully sanitize the oral cavity.

2. Despite the positive qualities of NOS, it should be used by the doctor strictly according to the indications, taking into account also possible contraindications to the procedure.

3. In the city of Chita, with a population of about 351,784 people, there are only 3 clinics equipped with modern equipment, where the NOS procedure is possible, which is not enough, and cannot adequately provide conditions for comfortable dental treatment in those ones having indications for it.

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